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Examination Of The Role Of Virtual Multisensory Integration In The Formation Of Emotional Regulation During Adaptation To Virtual Reality Environments

Contemporary research within the scope of virtual reality technologies focuses on understanding the specific features of human interaction with virtual environments, where multisensory integration acquires particular importance. This concept is understood as the coordinated processing of several types of sensory signals at once (visual, auditory, tactile, and others) that enter the brain. The integration of signals can substantially influence the formation and regulation of emotional reactions, because the naturalness of a user's perception of virtual space depends on its synchrony. In turn, successful integration determines the effectiveness of a person's adaptation to a new environment and expands the possibilities for the correction and development of emotional states by means of virtual reality technologies.

The neurophysiological mechanisms of multisensory integration in virtual reality play a key role in shaping the user's emotional reactions. In virtual reality, interaction with visual, auditory, tactile, and other sensory stimuli occurs simultaneously, which activates complex neural networks, in particular in the part of the brain that is responsible for emotional regulation-primarily the limbic system, the anterior cingulate cortex, and the insular cortex. The activation of these areas is conditioned by the coherent inflow of sensory information, and it is the synchrony or,

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on the contrary, the discrepancy between channels of stimulation that can substantially change the user's emotional state.

Recent studies demonstrate that virtual environments with multichannel sensory influences are capable of both enhancing emotional engagement and causing overload that reduces emotional reactivity. In particular, the study by M. Magalhães and et al. (2024) showed that the combination of positive stimuli, including touch and taste, is likely to evoke strong emotions in users; however, excessive sensory saturation can lead to cognitive overload and a decrease in emotional response (Magalhães et al., 2024). The results underscore the importance of balance between the quantity and quality of sensory channels when designing virtual reality experiences aimed at emotional regulation.

At the level of neural mechanisms, multisensory integration in virtual reality is also studied through experiments that modify visual and tactile information. Thus, in the study by K. Phataraphruk and et al. (2020), a change in motor behaviour in monkeys was recorded when varying visual feedback in a virtual reality environment, which indicates the plasticity of neural pathways of sensory information integration and its influence on decision making and emotional tuning (Phataraphruk et al., 2020). Similar results confirm that virtual reality activates existing sensory systems and creates unique conditions for their reorganization, which is significant for understanding adaptation to new emotional states. Owing to the possibility of simultaneously engaging several sensory channels-vision, hearing, touch, smell, or even taste-virtual reality designers can create emotionally rich scenarios that influence the psychophysiological states of users. The purposeful combination of sensory stimuli makes it possible not only to evoke particular emotions but also to gradually change or regulate them, which is especially useful in working with anxiety, post-traumatic stress disorder, mood disorders, or affective dysregulation.

The study by V. Sasu and et al. (2024) focused on the use of smells in combination with visual images to stimulate autobiographical memory in virtual reality. The results showed that aromatic stimuli presented in an appropriate context elicited strong positive emotions associated with childhood memories, which persisted

even after the experiment had ended. The study demonstrates the potential of virtual reality as a means of emotional regulation through the manipulation of sensory elements, especially in therapeutic contexts (Sasu et al., 2024). In the context of virtual reality, sensory coherence plays a critical role in reducing symptoms of discomfort, in particular anxiety, disorientation, or cybersickness, which arise as a result of sensory conflict between visual, vestibular, and somatosensory channels. When input stimuli from different sensory systems reach the brain in a coordinated manner, the likelihood of a negative emotional reaction decreases, which promotes emotional stabilization and the formation of a sense of presence in virtual space.

The introduction of new sensory channels, such as thermal or aromatic signals, provided that they are consistent with visual and auditory stimuli, can reduce stress levels in simulated extreme conditions. For example, in the work of X. Xia and et al. (2024), a virtual reality evacuation scenario was developed using thermal and aromatic feedback. The results showed that it was thermal stimulation synchronized with visual events that significantly increased the emotional engagement of participants, while at the same time reducing panic due to the predictability and sensory logic of the situation (Xia et al., 2024).

The analysis of empirical data provides grounds to assert that the rational combination of diverse sensory channels in virtual reality has significant potential for emotional regulation and can be successfully used in therapeutic and rehabilitation practices. At the same time, the question of finding an optimal balance between sensory loads remains important in order to avoid cognitive overload and to ensure stable positive results. Further research focused on the subtleties of the interaction between different sensory systems is promising for deepening the understanding of neurophysiological mechanisms and for improving virtual reality tools with consideration of users' individual characteristics.

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